

Knowledge and Practice Regarding Basic Life Support Among Nurses at Selected Private Hospitals, Kathmandu, Nepal

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ABSTRACT: Basic life support (BLS) is a life-saving method for the patient with the use of cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR), use of automated external defibrillator (AED) and airway management. The nurses need to have knowledge and proper skills regarding BLS to save the lives of patients at the hospital as well as in the community setup. Hence, the study aimed to assess the knowledge and practice regarding BLS among nurses at selected private hospitals in Kathmandu, Nepal. A descriptive, cross-sectional study design was carried out to collect data among the nurses working in Green City Hospital, Chirayu National Hospital and Medical Institute Pvt. Ltd and B.P Smriti Hospital using a self-administered semi-structured questionnaire. A sample of 136 nurses was taken using probability stratified random sampling technique. The study found that only 7.4% nurses had adequate level of knowledge, 51.5% had moderate level of knowledge and 41.1% had inadequate level of knowledge regarding BLS. The study also revealed that 65.4% nurses had good practice and 34.6% had poor practice regarding BLS. There was a statistically significant association between the level of knowledge and working ward ($p=0.002$), working experience ($p=0.011$) and training related to CPR ($p=0.000$). There was no significant association between level of practice regarding BLS and other sociodemographic and professional related variables. It is concluded that although the knowledge level regarding BLS is adequate among few nurses whereas there is good practice regarding BLS among more nurses.

KEYWORDS: Knowledge, Practice, Basic life support, Cardiopulmonary resuscitation .

I. INTRODUCTION

Basic Life Support (BLS) is the term for manual techniques used to protect the airway without the use of equipment¹. It is a life-saving method that includes instant recognition of cardiac arrest, initiation of emergency response systems, adoption of adequate cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR), implementation of rapid defibrillation and airway management².

BLS includes recognition of signs of sudden cardiac arrest (SCA), heart attack, stroke and foreign-body airway obstruction (FBAO); cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR); and defibrillation with an automated external defibrillator (AED)³. In a premedical setting, BLS is a life-saving procedure. For any healthcare professional working in a hospital, having sufficient knowledge and awareness of BLS and CPR is a fundamental requirement⁴. Defibrillation within 3 to 5 minutes of collapsed patients can produce survival rates as high as 50 to 70%. Each minute of delay to defibrillation reduces the probability of survival to hospital discharge by 10 percent⁵. A patient has a better chance of surviving if CPR is started as soon as possible. According to the American Heart Association, early CPR could save the lives of 100,000 to 200,000 adults and children each year. Studies have shown that even among highly trained professionals, such as doctors, nurses and others, the recall of CPR knowledge and abilities tends to decrease as early as three months after training if not in application⁶.

It is ultimately the responsibility of the health care professionals especially doctors and nurses to effectively manage an emergency condition where CPR may require. Inadequate training and the inability to manage medical emergencies might lead to legal problems in some situations. Thus, BLS with excellent CPR are among the crucial management until a medical emergency is treated definitely⁷. Most institutions have an essential requirement that all nurses have fundamental basic cardiac life support (BCLS) training⁸. The early response of nurses can have a major impact on the rates of morbidity and mortality associated with cardiac arrest with the application of BLS^{9,10}.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Methods

A descriptive cross-sectional research design was adopted for the study of the knowledge and practice regarding basic life support among nurses.

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B. Sampling and Setting

Probability stratified sampling technique was used among 136 nurses. The study was conducted in three private hospitals in Kathmandu, Nepal. Those were Green City Hospital, Chirayu National Hospital and Medical Institute Pvt. Ltd and B.P Smriti Hospital.

Instrumentation

Semi-structured self-administered questionnaire was administered which consisted of three parts:-

Part I: Socio-demographic and professional related information.

Part II: Questionnaire related to knowledge regarding BLS.

Part III: Checklist related to practice of BLS.

C. Data Collection

The researcher obtained permission to collect data from three different private hospitals' authorities. After then questionnaires were distributed to the nurses and collected soon after the nurses filled up the questionnaire.

Data Analysis

The collected data was checked, reviewed, and organized daily for its accuracy, completeness, and consistency. The data was coded and entered in Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 26.0 for data process and analysis. Data was analyzed by using simple descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. Inferential statistics like chi square test was used to identify the association between levels of knowledge and practice with selected variables.

III. RESULTS

Table 1. Socio Demographic Information of the Respondents n=136

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age (years)		
≤20	13	9.5
21-29	107	78.7
≥30	16	11.8
<i>Mean±SD 25.2±5.89; Min: 19 years; Max : 49years</i>		
Religion		
Brahman	37	27.2
Kshetri	25	18.4
Newar	19	14.0
Tamang	15	11.0
Magar	10	7.3
Gurung	13	9.6
Others*	17	12.5
Ethnicity		
Hinduism	107	78.7
Non-Hinduism**	29	21.3
Marital status		
Married	51	37.5
Unmarried	83	61.0
Other***	2	1.5

*Rai, Bishworkarma, Thakuri, Tharu **Buddhism, Christianity ***Divorced, Widow

Table 1 shows that 78.7% of the respondents belonged to 21-29 years of age group, 27.2% were Brahmin, 78.7% were Hindus and 61% were unmarried.

Table 2. Profession related Information of Respondents n=136

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Educational level		
Proficiency Certificate Level in Nursing (PCL)	87	64.0
Bachelor Nursing	49	36.0
Designation		
Staff nurse	123	90.4
In-charge and Senior staff nurse	13	9.6
Working ward		
Post-operative Ward	27	19.8

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Intensive Care Unit	25	18.3
General Ward	22	16.2
Emergency	20	14.7
Medical Ward	11	8.1
High Care Unit	11	8.1
Surgical Ward	10	7.4
Cabin	10	7.4
Working experience		
≤2 years	70	51.5
3-4 years	29	21.3
>4 years	37	27.2
Training related to CPR		
Yes	47	34.6
No	89	65.4
Previous involvement in CPR		
Yes	58	42.6
No	78	57.4

Table 2 reveals that 64% respondents had completed PCL nursing, 90.4% were staff nurses, 19.8% were from post-operative ward, 51.5% of the respondents had working experience of less than 2 years, 65.4% of the respondents had not received training of CPR and 57.4% had not involved in CPR.

Table 3. Knowledge regarding BLS among Respondents n=136

Statements	Frequency	Percentage
Meaning of BLS Care that is provided to anyone who is experiencing cardiac arrest, respiratory distress or an obstructed airway	68	50.0
Principles of CPR Circulation, airway, breathing	48	35.3
Steps to check normal breath of victim Look, listen and feel	117	86.0
Location for chest compression in adult At xiphisternum	46	33.8
Location for chest compression in infants One finger breadth below the nipple line	81	59.6
The ratio of chest compressions on an adult A rate of 100 to 120 compressions per minute and a depth of at least 2 inches	76	55.9
The ratio of chest compressions on pediatrics 30:2 for 1 provider, then switch to 15:2 for 2 providers	52	38.2
Most consider while giving mouth to mouth ventilation in adult Pinch nose	52	38.2
Rescue breathing in infants Only mouth to nose breathing	21	15.4
The preferred method for opening airway in head or neck trauma Jaw thrust	85	62.5
AED stands for Automated External Defibrillator	75	55.1
AED pad placement on infants Place 1 pad on the chest and another 1 pad on the back	87	64.0
EMS stands for Emergency Medical Services	80	58.8
The first response for choking Give abdominal thrusts	81	59.6
The most common complication of CPR Ribs fracture	126	92.6

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Table 3 reveals that 86% of the respondents gave right answer regarding the steps to check normal breath of the victim, 64% gave correct answer regarding the AED pad placement on infants and 92.6% gave correct answer regarding the most common complication of CPR,

Table 4. Level of Knowledge regarding BLS among Respondents n=136

Levels of Knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
Adequate (>11 of total score)	10	7.4
Moderate (8-11 of total score)	70	51.5
Inadequate (<8 of total score)	56	41.1

Table 4 shows that 7.4% of the respondents had adequate level of knowledge, 51.5% of the respondents had moderate level of knowledge, and 41.1% had inadequate level of knowledge regarding BLS.

Table 5. Practice regarding BLS among Respondents n=136

Statement	Frequency	Percentage
The initial BLS steps is to assess the victim, activate EMS and get AED, check pulse, start CPR.	113	83.1
The carotid pulse is felt before delivering CPR in adult.	87	64.0
Femoral pulse is felt before delivering CPR in infant.*	73	53.7
The airway is opened by tilting the head forward and lifting the chin.*	59	43.4
The depth of chest compression of adult is 2 inches.	86	63.2
The depth of chest compression of infant is about 1 inch.*	73	53.7
When 2 rescuers are present, switch the compression every minutes taking less than 2 seconds.*	54	39.7
The proper steps for operating an AED are power on the AED, attach electrode pads, analyze the rhythm and shock the person.	88	64.7
The recovery position is to lie the patient on their left side with the lower arm extended and upper leg flexed after CPR.	85	62.5
While performing Heimlich maneuver, the hand is placed slightly above the navel and below the lower part of the breastbone.	77	56.6

* Negative statement

Table 5 represents that 83.1% had provided the correct answer regarding the initial BLS steps for adults to assess the victim, activate EMS and get AED, check pulse, start CPR., 64.7% knew about the proper steps for operating an AED are power on the AED, attach electrode pads, analyze the rhythm and shock the person and 64% felt carotid pulse before delivering CPR in adult.

Table 6. Level of Practice regarding BLS among Respondents n=136

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Good Practice (>5 score)	89	65.4
Poor Practice (≤5 score)	47	34.6

Table 6 shows that 65.4% of the respondents had good practice and 34.6% had poor practice regarding BLS.

Table 7. Association between Respondents' Level of Knowledge and Selected Variables n=136

Variables	Level of Knowledge			χ^2	P value
	Adequate	Moderate	Inadequate		
Age					
≤20	9	4	0	5.585a	0.232
21-29	42	56	9		
≥30	5	10	1		
Education level				1.329 ^a	0.515
PCL Nursing	33	48	6		
Bachelor in Nursing	23	22	4		
Designation				2.316 ^a	0.314

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Staff nurse	52	61	10	33.677 ^a	0.002
In-charge/Senior staff nurse	4	9	0		
Working ward					
Post-operative ward	16	11	0		
Intensive Care Unit	5	18	2		
General ward	16	4	2		
Emergency	4	14	2		
Medical ward	6	4	1		
High care unit	2	9	0		
Surgical ward	2	7	1		
Cabin	5	3	2		
Working Experience				13.029 ^a	0.011
≤2 years	37	30	3		
3-4 years	8	20	1		
>4 years	11	20	6		
Training related to CPR				23.418 ^a	0.000
Yes	7	34	7		
No	49	36	3		
Previous involvement in CPR				1.915 ^a	0.384
Yes	21	31	6		
No	35	39	4		

Level of significant <0.05

Table 7 illustrates that there was statistically significant association between the level of knowledge regarding BLS and working ward (p=0.002), working experience (p=0.011) and training related to CPR (p=0.000).

Table 8. Association between Respondents' Level of Practice and Selected Variables n=136

Variables	Level of Practice		χ^2	P value
	Poor practice	Good practice		
Age			1.782 ^a	0.410
≤20	3	10		
21-29	40	67		
≥30	4	12		
Education level			0.602 ^a	0.438
PCL Nursing	28	59		
Bachelor in Nursing	19	30		
Designation			2.337 ^a	0.126
Staff nurse	45	78		
In-charge/Senior staff nurse	2	11		
Working ward			8.863 ^a	0.263
Post-operative ward	12	15		
Intensive Care Unit	10	15		
General ward	9	13		
Emergency	7	13		
Medical ward	3	8		
High care unit	2	9		
Surgical ward	0	10		
Cabin	4	6		
Working Experience			0.206 ^a	0.902

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≤2 years	25	45		
3-4 years	9	20		
>4 years	13	24		
Training related to CPR			0.954 ^a	0.329
Yes	14	34		
No	33	55		
Previous involvement in CPR			0.000 ^a	0.987
Yes	20	38		
No	27	51		

Level of significant <0.05

Table 8 reveals that there was no significant association between respondents' level of practice regarding BLS and selected variables.

IV. DISCUSSION

The findings of the present study showed that only 7.4% nurses had adequate level of knowledge, 51.5% had moderate level of knowledge and 41.1% had inadequate level of knowledge regarding BLS. The findings is somehow similar to the findings of a descriptive study conducted in Bharatpur, India among nursing staffs working in Government Medical College to assess the level of knowledge on which 10% nurses had good knowledge about BLS, while 50 % had moderate and 40 % nurses had poor knowledge².

The present study revealed that 65.4% respondents had good practice and 34.6% had poor practice regarding BLS which is similar to the findings of the study conducted in Ogun State, Nigeria which showed that 65.2% of the respondents had good practice and 34.8% had poor practice regarding BLS¹¹.

In this study, there was statistically significant association between the level of knowledge regarding BLS and working ward ($p=0.002$), working experience ($p=0.011$) and training related to CPR ($p=0.000$). Somehow similar findings was found in the study conducted in New Delhi, India which revealed that there was significant association of knowledge with experience, clinical area and in service education with p value<0.05¹².

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that very few had adequate level of knowledge, more than half of the nurses had moderate level of knowledge and about four in ten nurses had inadequate level of knowledge regarding BLS whereas the majority of the respondents had good level of practice and a few had poor practice regarding BLS. There was statistically significant association between the level of knowledge regarding BLS and working ward, working experience and training related to CPR. There was no significant association between respondents' level of practice regarding BLS and selected variables.

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